

Effect of azolla and N on rice grain and straw yield

S. M. Alam, Atomic Energy Agricultural Research Centre (AEARC), Tando Jam, Pakistan

We evaluated the relative advantage of using azolla *A. pinnata* as a supplemental source of N alone or in combination with N fertilizer in a pot experiment, 1988 wet season. Soil was silty clay loam, with pH 7.4, 1.03% organic C, 0.07% total N, 3 ppm available P, 0.78 meq exchangeable K/100 g soil, CEC 21 meq/100 g soil, and ECE 0.12%. Single superphosphate at

25 mg P/kg soil was applied basally to all pots.

Two levels of urea N, 30 mg N/kg soil and 60 mg N/kg soil, and one level of azolla N, 2.05 mg N/kg soil, were used in a randomized complete block design with four replications.

Fresh azolla, with 93.4% moisture content and (dry weight basis) 4.15% N, 0.45% P, 4.38% K, 0.35% Ca, and 1.42% Na was incorporated 1 d before transplanting rice cultivar IR8-5.

Azolla alone and with urea stimulated growth and significantly increased grain yield (see table). The order of yield increases was 30 mg N/kg

Effect of azolla and N on rice straw and grain yields. Tando Jam, Pakistan, 1988 wet season.

Treatment (per kg soil)	Straw yield (g/pot)	Grain yield (g/pot)
No N	21.96 e	8.24 e
750 mg fresh azolla	27.84 c	10.68 c
30 mg N	26.36 d	9.84 d
30 mg N + 750 mg fresh azolla	30.36 a	12.92 a
60 mg N	28.92 b	11.92 b

soil plus azolla > 60 mg N/kg alone > azolla alone > 30 mg N/kg alone > no N. Straw yield increased significantly with azolla. □

Disease management

Effect of N on bacterial leaf streak (BLS) and bacterial blight (BB) diseases in some scented rice varieties

P. Ranga Reddy, G. B. Manna, K. S. Rao, and B. T. S. Moorthy, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack 753006, India

Damage from BB caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* and BLS caused by *X. campestris* pv. *oryzicola* depends on the cultivar and on crop management practices. Degree of cultivar susceptibility and duration, N application method, and prevailing weather conditions influence the pattern of disease buildup. BLS becomes severe during incessant rain; BB increases gradually and spreads irrespective of weather.

We studied disease buildup in scented rice cultivars Basmati 370, Pakistan Basmati, T412, IET8580, IETS579, and Badshabhog under four N levels during 1988 wet season, in a random block design with two replications. Plot size was 2.25 × 4 m. N as urea was applied in 30-kg increments, from 0 to 90 kg N/ha, 50% at transplanting, 25% 20 d after transplanting, and 2.5% at panicle initiation. Disease was scored at 10-d intervals from 1 mo after transplanting

to panicle initiation. Severity was estimated as the percentage of leaf area damaged in each plot.

All six varieties were susceptible to BLS and BB, with disease severity depending on N level. Percentage of infected leaf area for both disease, varied among varieties. The analysis of variance was significant for N level, variety, and N × variety interaction for both diseases.

BLS incidence during early crop growth stages was severe in Basmati

1. Buildup of BLS and BB diseases in 4 rice varieties at 4 N levels. Cuttack, India, 1988 wet season.

370, IET8580, and Badshabhog, with 10 to 35% damage to leaf area, depending on N level; BLS was only 0-5% in Pakistan Basmati, IET8579, and T412. At 60 and 90 kg N/ha, disease severity increased between 35 and 45 d after transplanting (DT), with a steep decline thereafter (Fig. 1). This may be due to abundant availability of N initially, coupled with favorable weather conditions. Continuous rainfall during the season increased

2. Weekly averages of maximum and minimum temperature, rainfall, relative humidity, and sunshine hours during crop growth. Cuttack, India, 1988 wet season.

relative humidity to 90% and above and decreased number of sunshine hours. Temperatures remained optimum for multiplication of BLS (Fig. 2). The decrease in severity from 55 to 65 DT might be attributed to reduced available N and heavy rain that could have washed bacterial exudate

from the diseased leaves, limiting disease spread.

BB disease was severe at 60 and 90 kg N/ha, causing 15-42% leaf area damage in Pakistan Basmati, T412, IET8580, and IET8579. Basmati 370 and Badshahog suffered the least damage at all N levels. The disease

levels established during early growth stages gradually increased through the season, although peak incidence was between 35 and 45 DT. Disease intensity overlapped at 60 and 90 kg N/ha in Pakistan Basmati; intensity increased with increased N in IET8580 (Fig. 2). □

Rhizoctonia solani: an agent of rice boot blight

N. I. Singh, Km. R. K. T. Devi, and Kh. U. Singh, Botany and Plant Pathology Department, Manipur Agricultural College, Iroisemba, Imphal 795001, India

During disease surveys at different growth stages of rice in several rice-growing areas in Manipur 1978-88, we identified a severe boot blight disease.

The blight occurs on the uppermost leaf sheath enclosing young panicles. Early lesions are ellipsoid or ovoid greenish grey, coalescing to occupy the whole sheath. The center of lesions becomes greyish white with a brown margin. Sclerotia of the fungus forming on or near the affected area (see figure, a), are easily detached. Infected panicles rot within the sheath or emerge only partially. Infected grains become chaffy brown.

Sometimes a few panicle branches within an infected sheath emerge sidewise (see figure, b) and become chaffy.

We collected several samples of diseased rice and isolated the causal fungus on potato dextrose agar (PDA) slants. Mycelium is white when young, becoming brown and septate. Its internodal area range is $20 \times 120-40 \times 350 \mu\text{m}$. Sclerotia are more or less globose when young, becoming dark brown. Individual sclerotium measures as long as 4 mm.

Pathogenicity test was performed by inserting artificially infected rice grains or mature sclerotia inside the leaf sheaths enclosing young panicles. The causal fungus was identified as *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn, the causal agent of rice sheath and leaf blight. This is the first report of the occurrence of *R. solani* causing boot blight in India. □

Rice panicles infected with *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn, Imphal, India, 1988. A = fungal sclerotia, B = infected panicle branches.

Effect of roguing on rice tungro virus (RTV) incidence and rice yield

D. B. Estano, Entomology Department, IRRI; and B. M. Shepard, Clemson University, Coastal Research and Education Center, Charleston, South Carolina 29414, USA

RTV is controlled by planting resistant rice varieties. However, resistance has broken down in many areas. In these cases, early insecticide application and frequent removal, or roguing, of diseased rice plants are recommended. The principle behind roguing is to remove the source of inoculum, reducing the chances of disease spread by the green leafhopper (GLH) vector.

We transplanted 21-d-old seedlings of rice variety IR42 (moderately resistant to GLH, susceptible to RTV), on a 1/8 ha field at IRRI farm in 1988 wet season. The area was divided into 12 plots; 6 were rogued, 6 were not. RTV-infected hills were rogued and replaced with healthy plants from adjacent hills beginning 14 d after transplanting (DT) and continuing weekly to 60 DT.

RTV-infected hills were counted at 30, 45, and 60 DT. Grain yield was taken from the center of each plot, leaving two border rows.

RTV was significantly lower in rogued than in nonrogued plots at 45 and 60 DT, but yields did not differ significantly (see table). Yields were

RTV incidence and yield of IR42 in rogued and nonrogued plots.^a IRRI, 1988 wet season.

Plot treatment	RTV incidence (%)			Grain yield (t/ha)
	30 DT	45 DT	60 DT	
Rogued	1.9 a	7.2 a	12.0 a	1.8 a
Nonrogued	3.2 a	18.0 b	29.7 b	1.7 a

^aDT = days after transplanting. In a column, treatment means having a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

low with and without roguing.

Our conclusion is that, while roguing may help reduce RTV incidence, it is not likely to help if RTV intensity is high. □